

Examining Factors Affecting the Growth of Horticulture Sector in Kenya**(Case Study of Rarieda District a long Lake Victoria)****Kennedy Danga**

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Abstract

This study based its findings on population of 681 farmers. The researcher opted for 10% of accessible population to facilitate a concise sample size which was belief to be more accurate for collecting the required information. Thus, 68 farmers of the accessible respondents were drawn to represents the entire population. The instrument used to collect data was questionnaires which were self administered. Research findings were; majority of the respondents were age 45 and above. Secondly, majority were form four levers and primary school dropout, this was attributed by lack fee to proceed to next level of education. Thirdly, majority of respondents strongly agreed that lack of credited facilities, initial capital to enable farmers make use of unutilized land, lack of ready market and lack of basic farming knowledge hindered horticultural growth in Kenya. On the other hand, majority of respondents strongly disagreed that perception and non lucrateness affect horticulture growth. Recommendations made were Government should offer incentives to youth and women to encourage them to practice horticultural farming so that agriculture should not be left in the control of the older and aging farmers. Government and Non-Governmental Organization should offer incentives programme e.g. offering capital and credits facilities so that farmers can invest in agriculture and buy modern farming technology. To solve the problem of lack of ready market, both national and county governments should ensure that all farmers can access information of the market in foreign country and local. The country government should established processing plant to deal with excess surplus of farm products and do value addition of those products. Lastly, both governments should introduce a policy where land should not lie idle especial in areas where horticultural can be practised and provide initial capital for farmers so that they invest and start farming on those idle lands.

Keywords: economic constraints factors, social constraints factors, environmental constraints factors, horticultural farming, modern horticulture technology

CHAPTER ONE**INTRODUCTION****1.0 Introduction**

This chapter discusses the back ground of study and statement of the problem, objective, research questions and limitation. It also explains the significance of this study and examines factors affecting the growth of horticulture sector in Kenya

1.1 Background of study

Over the year rain water has continue to become scarce and less reliable in many part of the world Kenya included. This has been contributed by destruction of Ozone layer which is being destroyed by greenhouse gases. This effect has distorted the global climate pattern, therefore, making the rain to be unpredictable. Kenya like any part of Africa and the world are experiencing effect of climate change and encroaching drought. This has made people to rethink of new technology of farming because rain fed agriculture can no longer work anymore.

The unreliable rainfall has made hunger to be a challenge to the world, hence threatening the lives of many across the world especially in most part of Africa at this time when population is increasing. Therefore, horticultural farming remains the only way forward for good farming. It involves the use of drip irrigation system in an open field or in greenhouse farming. This method of farming has work in Israel and Egypt, which are also affected by dry condition/drought than our country. It's also a good method of practising sustainable farming which can produce high quality yield while conserving water and soil in that, our future generation will also enjoy same resources. According to farmers who are practising horticulture farming said that, it has transformed their lives because they generate allot of income and can now live dignify life. It remains the only method of farming in which farmers can overcome effect of climate change which has adversely affect farming and food security in the world. Secondly, it's a good method which can compensate owners of land the value of their money because poor conventional farming method have caused loss to farmers and cannot generate enough income for the use of land resource. This has forced farmers to sale

their land or convert it from farming to real estate which has a bigger return on investment. Therefore, horticultural remain the only farming method in which farmers can earn same return for the value of their land.

This type of farming still faces some problems in our country whose majority of the population is youth and comprises more than 60% of the population. According to literature, it is believed that the youth can effectively and efficiently implement this method. Secondly, many farmers have trouble in getting the right information regarding to quality of seeds, agrichemical, good drip irrigation system and greenhouse. This is because most of the farming is being done in rural areas where majority of the householders lack electricity and fibre optic making it difficult for them to access internet which today is the source of acquiring information. Third, problem is that to invest in horticultural technology also require a larger capital which majority of the farmers can rarely afford, this making only few farmers who can have access to loan to borrow and buy the required facilities needed. Lastly, poor land policy in the country has led to poor management of land; either the lands have been sub divided into unproductive pieces or left lying idle. If these unutilized lands are put into good farming system our economic growth can increase if not dupable.

A well implemented horticultural in the country will boost our export because we will be producing more than enough and export the surplus to other countries thus earning more foreign exchange. Our agricultural sector will also create more jobs to our youth and also secure food security which is becoming a threat to our country. Poverty will now become a thing of past as majority will benefit either direct or indirect from this sector.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Horticulture is the only way in which we can achieve food security and create employment among our unemployed youth, eradicate poverty, ensure economic growth of our GNP and at the sometime practising sustainable agribusiness which will enable us produce high quality yield, while conserving water and soil in that future generation will also be able to enjoy same resource. No country can develop without proper food security in place, even first world countries like Britain and America first practise agriculture before they think of industrialization. By using modern horticulture technology, we will be in position to attain the vision 2030.

There are still many challenges faced by farmers who are willing to start this project, some of them are poor government policy, youth perception and altitude toward farming, lack of capital to investment in farming, lack of information where they can find quality products such hybrid seeds, agrichemical fertilizers, drip system and green house sheets. The purpose of this research was to examining factors affecting the growth of horticulture sector in Kenya. This study measures various variables which were considered to be important factors affecting horticulture farming. It also came up with policies needed to be done in order to encourage horticulture farming in the country.

1.3 Main Objective of the Study

Was to examining factors affecting the growth of horticulture sector in Kenya and how it could be solved.

1.3.1 Specific Objective

- a. Was to identify main economic constraints which affect growth of horticulture sector.
- b. Was to find out some social factors affecting growth of horticulture
- c. Was to try to find out which environmental constraints hindering growth.

1.4 Research Questions

1. Do economic constraints factors have affect the growth of horticulture?
2. Do social constraints factors affect horticultural growth and discourage farmers to involve in horticulture farming?
3. Do environmental constraints factors affect participating people in horticultural farming?

1.5 Significant of the Study

The study was importance to people of Rarieda and the whole country in general and any other organization who were interested in selling or venturing in the horticultural farming. Farmers can use this study's finding to know the importance of horticultural farming to the economy of our country. For instance, farmers can be self employed so that they can get income and be self reliable. Both national and county government can use this study to know more about factors which hinders horticulture farming and how they can leverage them to the benefit this country. Others stakeholders like nongovernmental organisation can also use it to further their knowledge concerning horticultural farming in the country.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study was conducted in Rarieda district along Lake Victoria, about 68 farmers were sampled in the population of 681 farmers using convenience sampling method.

1.7 Limitation of the Study

The available data and information in same organizations such as Amiran and Horticultural Crops Development Authority (HCDA) could not be really upon as farmers don't know existence of these organizations and were unwilling to give them the data. Hence this study relied on direct contact with the farmers in order to get the right information through observation and questionnaires to get data and information.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

In this chapter provides the reader with summary of literature, theoretical review and also gives an explanation of theoretical and frame work of the problem being study, empirical review and conceptual frame work of the study.

2.1 Summary of the Literature Review

Available literature points to the fact that agriculture remains a key sector where the surplus unemployed youthful labour force can be employed in Africa. Agriculture currently plays a major role in the lives of the many young people and it is projected to remain so even in the next few decades, FAC (2010). There are many factors which affect youth involvement in horticultures. The decision to migrate involves both "push" and "pull" factors Lewis, (1954); and Harris and Todaro, (1970). The 'push factors' include declining national resources; increasing cost of social amenities; loss of employment, oppressive religious, ethnic or political concerns; alienation from community; lack of opportunities for personal development, and/or effect of natural disaster. The 'pull factors' are the likelihood of better employment opportunities; good educational facilities; diversified opportunities, and better recreational activities. Bogue, (1969). While empirical study done by Adekunle *et al.* (2006) point out inadequate credit facility, lack of agricultural insurance, poor returns to agricultural investment, lack of basic farming knowledge and lack of access to tractors and other farm inputs as the major constraints hindering youth participation in agriculture.

To further attract the youth into agriculture, deliberate efforts by agro-support agencies to make inputs such as good seed, fertilizers, basic mechanization and agricultural market information available and affordable should be undertaken Mbeine(2012). Jong-Dae (2012) argues that the very high population growth and growing percentage of the youth in the population need not be seen as liabilities but rather as assets for transforming Ugandan agriculture The youth possess unique capabilities (dynamism, strength, adventure, ambition), and these are assets for agriculture Nnadi and Akwiwu (2008). Youths represent the most active segment of the population and the engine that do most productive work of the society Adesope (1996). The youth have also been identified as constituting the major resource base for any country which wishes to embark on any meaningful agricultural and rural development projects Onuekwusi (2005).

2.2 Theoretical Review

The research reviewed some theories which were conducted by various scholars on agricultural growth decline which are related to the current study of the research, and also provided important information relevant to the study and helped the researcher to determined various variable that influenced framers involvement in horticultural growth. The theories discussed here are, "push" and "pull" theories which duel

main on migration phenomenon theory which linked decline in participation of the farmers in agricultural production to the rural-urban. The decision to migrate involves both “push” and “pull” factors Lewis (1954); Harris and Todaro (1970). The ‘push factors’ include declining national resources; increasing cost of social amenities; loss of employment, oppressive religious, ethnic or Political concerns; alienation from community; lack of opportunities for personal development, and/or effect of natural disaster. The ‘pull factors’ are the likelihood of better employment opportunities; good educational facilities; diversified marriage opportunities, and better recreational activities. Bogue, (1969).

Lack of incentives and drudgery are some of the reasons why the farmers are disinterested in agriculture IFAD, (2011). FAC (2010) underscores the current limited effort by most governments to engage the youth in agriculture and target the youth specifically with a view to understanding the constraints they face and devise plausible solutions to overcome them.

In the same vein, because traditional agriculture is based on the hand hoe and other rudimentary tools, subsistence agriculture holds no interest or appeal for young people. Unimproved conditions in Ugandan agricultural have rendered agriculture unattractive to the youth, Youth in Farming, (2011). Suriname (2011) further points out that the poor image of persons involved in agriculture needs to be changed and the young people are the ideal catalysts for such change given their greater propensity and willingness to adopt new ideas, concepts and technology which are all critical to changing the way agriculture is practiced and perceived. The current trend however is that so many youth are leaving agriculture even with the increased government support due to various reasons: Young people perceive agriculture as a profession of intense labour, not profitable and unable to support their livelihood compared to what white collar jobs offer, Youth in Farming (2011).

2.3 Theoretical Frame Work

Fig.2.1 Theoretical Frame Work

Source Author (2016)

2.4 Empirical Review

Akpan (2010) points out that some empirical studies found that economic push factors (such as, the lack of rural credit, unemployment, and rural poverty among others) are most important; while economic pull factors (such as, perception of high wages from urban employment) are dominant. This predisposition is used to help explain why there is a declining involvement of the youth in agriculture in Uganda.

Adekunle *et al.* (2006) point out inadequate credit facility, lack of agricultural insurance, poor returns to agricultural investment, lack of basic farming knowledge and lack of access to tractors and other farm inputs as the major constraints hindering youth participation in agriculture. Considering the individual characteristics, some of the authors for example, Sharma (2007) have found higher education and greater number of skills to lead to greater probability to leave agriculture. In the same vein, because traditional agriculture is based on the hand hoe and other rudimentary tools, subsistence agriculture holds no interest or appeal for young people. Unimproved conditions in Ugandan agricultural have rendered agriculture unattractive to the youth, Youth in Farming, (2011d). These factors have been identified primarily through

surveys, Adekunle et al. (2009). From the literature review, there are economic, social and environmental factors reducing rural youth involvement in agricultural production in Nigeria. Economic factors include inadequate credit facilities, low farming profit margins, and a lack of agricultural insurance, initial capital and production inputs. Social factors include public perception about farming and parental influence to move out of agriculture. Environmental issues include inadequate land, continuous poor harvests, and soil degradation. These findings are largely in agreement with the results obtained from the interviews conducted with selected youth leaders. The results further reveal that economic based constraints seem to be the most important factor.

2.5 Conceptual Frame Work

Fig 2.2 Conceptual Frame Work

Source (author, 2016)

CHAPTER THREE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter discusses research methodology by looking at research design, target population, sampling design, data collection and presentation.

3.1 Research Design

Bryman, A. (2001), defined research design as the scheme, outline or plan that is used to generate answers to the research problem. Descriptive research design was used in this study. It was appropriate because it facilitated a general understanding and interpretation of the problem and described the state of affairs as it was in that particular time. A major characteristic of descriptive was to provide information on the characteristics of a population or phenomenon.

3.2 Target Population

Population refers to the entire group of individual, event or object having common observable characteristics, Mugenda A. G. (2008) describe population as complete set of individual or object with same common characteristics to which researcher want to generalize the result of the study. This study was carried out in Rarieda District long the shore of Lake Victoria with a target population of 681 farmers.

Table 3.1 Population of Farmers

Classification	Population
Farmers with green house	81
Seasonal farmers with no irrigation	359
Farrows irrigation farmers (open farming)	241
Total Population	681

Source author, (2016)

3.3 Sample Size

According to Cooper D. R., & Schindler, P. S. (2006) sample is a small part of the study draws in such a way that the sample statistics represents the entire population. In this study, the sample size depends on the number of variable in the study. In this study the researcher opted for 10% of accessible population to facilitate a concise sample size which was more accurate for collecting the required information. The table below show 68 samples of farmers of the accessible respondents who were drawn to represents the entire population. Convenience sampling method was used because farmers were using different methods of farming according to their capital ability. This study classified farmers as show below where convenience sampling method used to draw sample.

Table 3.2 Sampling

Classification	Population	Sample
Farmers with green house	80	8
Seasonal farmers with no irrigation	360	36
Farrows irrigation farmers (open farming)	240	24
Total Population	480	68

Source Author, (2016)

3.4 Data Collection Methods

The researcher in this study used primary data to collect the accurate information needed for this research, this method was most economical, required little time to administrated and allow large collection of data. To collect primary data the researcher used questionnaires, which were self administered by researcher and delivering it to the farmers (samples) under the study and collect them after few days. The advantage was that the researcher personally introduced and explained to respondents the importance of the study. The researcher also explained questionnaires to the respondents and clarified any doubt or question that might arise.

3.5 Data Analysis and Presentation.

Data analysis was done careful to the collected data before representation. The collected data was edited, tabulated, classified and represented with tables and charts. The main aim was to help the users of the study to understand the entire information and facts gathered in an effective manner.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

4.0 Introductions

This chapter discusses the analysis of the data collected from the study conducted in Rarieda district, the data was interpreted in the relation to the objective and the research questions. Data were analysed using descriptive statics tools, such as charts and graphical presentation and conclusion was made base on the research findings.

4.1 Response Rate Analysis

The data were derived from structural questionnaires and administered to respondents. Table 4.1 shows the total number of sample group picked from total population. All questionnaires were received back.

Table 4.1 Response Rate Analysis

Classification	Population	Sample	percentage
Farmers with green house	81	8	100
Seasonal farmers with no irrigation	359	36	100
Farrows irrigation farmers (open farming)	241	24	100
Total Population	681	68	100

Source (Author, 2016)

4.3 Quantitative Analysis

Descriptive research was used in this study because it describes situation of the population being study as it exists and not the cause of it. Therefore, it was desirable to use descriptive research because it provides a systematic description that was factual and accurate as possible.

4.3.1 Gender Representation

Table 4.2 Gender Representation

Gender	Frequency	Percentages
Female	44	65
Male	24	35
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.2 Gender Representation

Source Author, (2016)

Majority of the respondents were male who had 65% response rate against their female colleagues who has a rate of 35%. Female have not embarrassed farming because majority were more interest in selling farms' products in the market than doing practical farming.

4.3.2 Summary of Respondent According to Age

Table 4.3 Respondent According to Age

Age In Years	Frequency	Percentage
18—25	8	12
26—35	12	18

36—45	14	20
45 and above	34	50
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.3 Respondent According To Age

Source Author, (2016)

Majority of the respondents were age 45 and above which was represent 50% followed by 36—45 which was represented by 20%. This means that majority of the farmers were middle age people but not youth. This might have been be contributed by the fact that youth perception and altitude toward agriculture is not good and also most of them are still interested searching for white colour job in urban areas.

4.3.3 Response on the Number of Years Farming

Table 4.4 Response on the Number of Years Farming

Years	Frequency	Percentage
0 – 6	40	59
6 – 10	17	25
11 – 14	8	12
15 – 20	3	4
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.4 response on the number of the year farming

Source Author, (2016)

The data depict that majority of the respondents have been doing farming between 0 - 6 which was represented by 59%. This might have been contributed by the effect of water hyacinth in the lake making majority to shift from fishing to horticulture farming, because it has disrupted fish breeding areas in the lake. Another factor was that the strangulated fish stock in the lake made many people to start horticulture as source of income in community where fishing was livelihood. Lastly, the change of weather pattern and unreliability of the rain has made some people to venture in horticulture than to wait for unpredictable rain.

4.3.4 Level of Education

Table 4.5 Summary of the Level of Education

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage
Primary	16	23
Secondary	40	59
College	8	12
University	4	6
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.5 Summary of the Level of Education

Source Author, (2016)

The summary basically means that the entire respondents were from four levers who were 59% of the respondents, followed by primary school dropouts who were 23%. This indicates that lack fees to proceed to next level of education might have forced them to start practising horticultural farming to get in income.

4.4 Qualitative Analysis

This is where data is analysed base on the judgmentally of an individual’s personal opinion his/her experienced and what he/she believed on.

4.4.1 Inadequate credit facilities

About 82% of the respondents strongly agreed that lack of credited facilities hindered grow of horticulture sector. Only 18% agreed that inadequate credited facilities have some impact on growth of horticultures. Majority said that these have made not buy modern farming equipment making their production to be low. The table below show analysis of respondents responses on inadequate create facilities.

Table 4.6 Response on Inadequate Credit Facilities

	Frequency	Percentage
I Strongly Agreed	56	82
I Agree	12	18
I Strongly Disagree	0	0
I Disagree	0	0
Am Neutral	0	0
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.6 Response on Inadequate Credit Facilities

Source Author, (2016)

4.4.2 Low Profits Margin

Majority of the respondents which was 47% strongly disagreed that low profit margin has effect on horticulture growth. With 18% of respondent agreed that low profits margin has some impact on growth of horticulture. 15% of the respondents strongly agreed that low profit margin is affecting the performance of horticulture sector, 11% disagreed. Majority of farmers ventured into farming with a lot optimistic with the aim of making profit with same committing all their saving or borrowing. In same case they end up making losses thus discourage them from continuing with farming and some are even being auctioned by financial institution to recover the loan.

Table 4.7 Response on Low Profits Margin

	Frequency	Percentage
I Strongly Agreed	10	15%
I Agree	12	18%
I Strongly Disagree	32	47%
I Disagree	8	11%
Am Neutral	6	9%
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.7 Response on Low Profits Margin

Source Author, (2016)

4.4.3 Initial capital

85% of respondents strongly agreed that initial capital was one of the economic factors which hindered the growth of horticulture sectors, 12% agreed and only 3% disagreed that it was not the major factor which affect the growth of horticulture. Majority said that these have hindered them to expand their farming while other said that they could start farming in unutilized land because they lack initial capital.

Table 4.8 Response on Initial capital

	Frequency	Percentage
I Strongly Agreed	58	85%
I Agree	8	12%
I Strongly Disagree	2	3%
I Disagree	0	0%
Am Neutral	0	0%
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.8 Response on Initial capital

4.4.4 Perception of Agriculture

Majority of the respondents which represent 71% strongly disagreed that perception of the agricultural sector is one of the social contract which hinders growth of horticulture. 13% also disagreed, 9% strongly agreed and 4% agreed that perception of agriculture affect it growth. Majority said that initial perception of agriculture hindered farming but many farmers who have invest modern farming were living successful live and were able to educate their children. These made people to see farming like any other form of employment.

Table 4.9 Response on Perception of Agriculture

	Frequency	Percentage
I Strongly Agreed	6	9%
I Agree	3	4%
I Strongly Disagree	48	71%
I Disagree	9	13%
Am Neutral	2	3%
Total	68	100

Fig 4.9 Response on Perception of Agriculture

Source Author, (2016)

4.4.5 Lack of Ready Market

Lack of ready market is one of the factors which hindered the growth of horticulture this was concluded as majority of respondents of 70% strongly agreed, followed by 18% who agreed. 6% of the respondents strongly disagreed and agreed lack of ready market has not impact on the growth of agriculture. Majority said that like of ready market hindered them because sometimes it forces them to sell their products at throw away price as supply exceed demand making to depend on brokers.

Table 4.10 Response on Lack of Ready Market

	Frequency	Percentage
	48	70%
I Agree	12	18%
I Strongly Disagree	4	6%
I Disagree	4	6%
Am Neutral	0	0%
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.10 Response on Lack of Ready Market

Source Author, (2014)

4.4.6 Non Lucrativeness of Agriculture

67% of the respondents strongly disagreed that non lucrateness of agriculture sectors was one of the factors which hinders it growth with 18% agreed.7% strongly agreed and 4% agreed that non lucrateness of agriculture has some impacts on it growth. Majority said that farming is becoming lucrative especially to farmers who have invested in modern technology because they supply quality products when seasons of farm products have good market especially when demand exceeds supply.

Table 4.11 Response on Non Lucrativeness of Agriculture

	Frequency	Percentage
I Strongly Agreed	5	7%
I Agree	3	4%
I Strongly Disagree	45	67%
I Disagree	12	18%
Am Neutral	3	4%
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.11 Response on Non Lucrativeness of Agriculture

4.4.7 Unutilized Land

Unutilized land along the lake was one of major factors which affect horticulture farming this was concluded because 78% of the respondents strongly agreed and 14% agreed. 4% of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed. Majority wrote that this was attributed by lack of capital to start farming.

Table 4.12 Response on Inadequate Land

	Frequency	Percentage
I Strongly Agreed	53	78%
I Agree	9	14%
I Strongly Disagree	3	4%
I Disagree	3	4%
Am Neutral	0	0%
Total	68	100

Fig 4.12 Response on Inadequate Land

4.4.8 Continuous Poor Harvest

54% of the respondents strongly agreed that continuous poor harvest has some affect on the growth of agriculture with 18% of respondents sharply contract them saying that continues poor harvest was not one of the factors which stagnant the growth of horticulture. Majority said that these all affect new farmers who expect pump harvest and end up not meeting their expectation, hence they are being discourage poor harvest to continue with farming.

Table 4.13 Response on Continuous Poor Harvest

	Frequency	Percentage
I Strongly Agreed	12	19%
I Agree	8	12%
I Strongly Disagree	37	54%
I Disagree	7	10%
Am Neutral	4	6%
Total	68	100

Fig 4.13 Response on Continuous Poor Harvest

Source Author, (2016)

4.4.9 Lack of Basic Farming Knowledge

Lack of basic farming knowledge was found to be one of the factors which hindered the growth of horticulture as 66% of the respondents strongly agreed with 12% strongly disagreed. 7% of respondents

agreed that basic farming knowledge has some impact on the growth of horticulture sector. This was one of the factors which lead to poor harvest and low production of farm products.

Table 4.14 Response on Lack of Basic Farming Knowledge

	Frequency	Percentage
I Strongly Agreed	45	66%
I Agree	7	10%
I Strongly Disagree	8	12%
I Disagree	6	9%
Am Neutral	2	3%
Total	68	100

Source Author, (2016)

Fig 4.14 Response on Lack of Basic Farming Knowledge

Source Author, (2016).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

The purpose of this study was to examining factors affecting the growth of horticulture sector in Kenya, (Case Study of Rarieda District a long Lake Victoria). This chapter mainly discusses the summary of the findings, conclusion and recommendation of the study.

5.1 Summary of the Finding

5.1.1 Demographic Information

Majority of the respondents were male who had 65% response rate against their female colleagues who has a rate of 35%. Majority of the respondents were age 45 and above which is 50% followed by 36- 45 which was 20%. This means that majority of the farmers were middle age people but not youth. Analysis depicted that majority of the respondents have been doing farming between 0 – 6 represented by 59%. The summary basically means that the entire respondents were form four levers who were 59% of the respondents, followed by primary school dropouts who were 23%.

5.1.2 Economic Constraints Factors

About 82% of the respondents strongly agreed that lack of credited facilities hindered the growth of horticulture sector. Only 18% agreed that inadequate credited facilities have some impact on growth of horticultures.

Majority of the respondents which was 47% strongly disagree that low profit margin has any effect on horticulture growth. With 18% of respondent agreed that low profits margin has some impact on growth of horticulture. 15% of the respondents strongly agreed that low profit margin is affecting the performance of horticulture sector, 11% disagreed.

85% of respondents strongly agreed that initial capital was one of the economic factors which hinder the growth of horticulture sectors, 12% agreed and only 3% disagreed that it was not of the major factor which affect the growth of horticulture.

5.1.3 Social Contracts Factors

Majority of the respondents which represent 71% strongly disagreed that perception of the agricultural sector is one of the social contract which hindered growth of horticulture. 13% also disagreed, 9% strongly agreed and 4 agree that perception of agriculture affect it growth.

Lack of ready market was one of the factors which hindered the growth of horticulture this was concluded as majority of respondents who represented 70% strongly agreed, followed by 18% who agreed. 6% of the respondents strongly disagreed and agreed lack of ready market has not impact on the growth of agriculture.

67% of the respondents strongly disagreed that non lucrateness of agriculture sectors was one of the factors which hinders it growth with 18% agreed. 7% strongly agreed and 4% agreed that non lucrateness of agriculture has some impacts on it growth.

5.1.4 Environmental Contracts Factors

Unutilized land along the lake was one of the major factors which hinder farming, this was concluded because 78% of the respondents strongly agreed and 14% agreed. 4% of the respondents strongly disagreed.

54% of the respondents strongly disagreed that continuous poor harvest has some affect on the growth of agriculture with 18% of respondents sharply contract them saying that continues poor harvest was one factors which stagnant the growth of horticulture.

Lack of basic farming knowledge was found to be one of the factors which hindered the growth of horticulture as 66% of the respondents strongly agreed with 12% strongly disagreed. 7% of respondents agree that basic farming knowledge has some impact on the growth of horticulture sector.

5.2 Conclusion

5.2.1 Demographic Information

Majority of the respondents were male who had 65% response rate against their female colleagues who has a rate of 35%. This indicates that, female were more interested in selling farms' products than actual farming. Majority of the respondents were middle aged farmers as compared to youth. Lack of incentives and drudgery are some of the reasons why the youth are disinterested in agriculture and also Rural-Urban drifts, that is, people leaving the village for jobs in the city. Lastly, Young people also preferred white collar jobs where they could dress impressively.

5.2.2 Economic Constraints Factors

About 82% and 85% of respondents strongly agreed that lack of credited facilities and initial capital respectively hinder the growth of horticulture. Lack of capital and credit facilities make farmers not to buy good seed, fertilizers, basic farm machines and green house sheet. This has made farmers really on poor farm tools instead of using modern agricultural machines like ridges, ploughs, and cultivators.

5.2.3 Social Contracts Factors

Lack of ready market was one of the factors which hindered the growth of horticulture this was concluded as majority of respondents, who represented 70% strongly agreed. Many farmers said that lack of ready market

has increased the activities of middlemen in buying of agricultural products from their farm at low prices hence discourage them. Perishable crops for example tomatoes, peppers and cabbages are affected while they are looking for market.

Unutilized land along the lake was one of the major factors which affect farming, this was concluded because 78% of the respondents strongly agreed. Land is one of the most important factors in agricultural production. The prevailing land tenure systems discourage agricultural land utilization because most of the lands along the lake were not cultivated because the owner could not have initial capital to start farming making the land to lie idle.

Lack of basic farming knowledge was found to be one of the factors which hindered the growth of horticulture as 66% of the respondents strongly agreed. Most of the farmers were not educated enough in the technicalities relating to agricultural product making them not to apply correct fertilizers, insecticides and even how to use new farm tools.

5.3 Recommendations

Government should offer incentives to youth and women to encourage them to practice horticultural farming so that agriculture should not be left in the control of the older and aging farmers. Government and Non-Governmental Organization should initiate incentives programme which can offer capital to farmers and credits facilities so that farmers can have enough money needed for them to invest in agriculture and buy modern farming technology. To solve the problem of lack of ready market, both national and county governments should ensure that all farmers can access information of the market both in foreign country and local. Lack of ready market can also be solved if country government established processing plant to deal with excess surplus of farm products and also do value addition of those products. Lastly, both governments should introduce a policy where land should not lie idle especial in areas where horticultural can be practised and also provide initial capital for farmers so that they invest and start farming on those idle lands.

5.3.1 Demographic Information

Government should offer incentives to youth and women to encourage them to practice farming so that agriculture should not be left in the control of the olders and aging farmers. This would encourage more food production and reduced food security in the country and the surplus to be exported.

5.3.2 Economic Constraints Factors

Government and Non-Governmental Organization initiated programme which could offer capital to farmers and credits facilities so that farmers can have enough money needed to invest in agriculture and buy modern farming technology like greenhouses, drip irrigation pipes and good seeds. Such initiatives for instances agro Vijana loan should be fully implemented to offer loan to young farmers.

5.3.3 Social Contracts Factors

Lack of ready market both national and county governments should ensure that all farmers can access information of the market through use of internet to look for market in foreign countries. Programmes such as free wifi zones can enable farmers look for market abroad for their products. Lack of ready market can also be solved if country government established processing plant to deal with excess surplus of farm products and also do value addition of those products. Good roads and storage facilities also will help farmers to transport their perishable products in time to the market.

5.3.4 Environmental Contracts Factors

Government should introduced a policy where land should not lie idle especial in areas where horticultural can be practised, this would increased more land to be cultivate hence more food production in the country. Government and Non-Governmental should tried to introduced educational programmes to farmers so that they could know how to use fertilizers, insecticides and new farm tools. All these would bring about low agricultural productivity.

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Appendix**Questionnaire**

Dear, Respondent

The questionnaire is prepared for the purpose of collecting data. Information and data you will provide will be treated with confidentiality and used only for this academic research.

You are requested to answer all questions.

Your corporation will be highly appreciated.

Section A: Demographic Information

Please tick where appropriate

- | | | | |
|----|---|---------|------------|
| 1. | Gender | male | female |
| 2. | Age | 18—25 | 26—35 |
| | | 36—45 | |
| 3. | Level of education | Primary | Secondary |
| | | College | University |
| 4. | Number of years you had been doing farming? | 0 – 6 | 6 – 10 |
| | | 11 – 14 | 15 – 20 |

Section B: Economic Constraints Factors

- | | | | | | |
|----|--|-----------------|---------|---------------------|------------|
| 5. | Do inadequate credit facilities effect growth of horticulture? | Strongly agreed | I agree | I strongly disagree | I disagree |
| | | Am neutral | | | |
| 6. | Does low farming profit margin affect growth of horticulture? | Strongly agreed | I agree | I strongly disagree | I disagree |
| | | Am neutral | | | |
| 7. | Does initial capital affect growth of horticulture? | Strongly agreed | I agree | I strongly disagree | I disagree |
| | | Am neutral | | | |

Section C: Social Constraints Factors

- | | | | | | |
|-----|---|-----------------|---------|---------------------|------------|
| 8. | Does perception of agriculture can affect growth of horticulture? | Strongly agreed | I agree | I strongly disagree | I disagree |
| | | Am neutral | | | |
| 9. | Lack of ready market can effect affect growth of horticulture? | Strongly agreed | I agree | I strongly disagree | I disagree |
| | | Am neutral | | | |
| 10. | Non lucrativeness of agriculture affects growth of horticulture? | Strongly agreed | I agree | I strongly disagree | I disagree |

Am neutral

Section D: Environmental Constraints Factors

11. Does unutilized of land of can affects growth of horticulture?
Strongly agreed I agree I strongly disagree I disagree

Am neutral

12. Does continuous poor harvests affects growth of horticulture?
Strongly agreed I agree I strongly disagree I disagree

Am neutral

13. Does lack of basic farming knowledge affects growth of horticulture?
Strongly agreed I agree I strongly disagree I disagree

Am neutral

Section E: Additional Comments

Any own opinion which challenges affects horticulture sectors?

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Thank you for assisting me.